

EMERALD

Deliverable D1.2

Data Modelling and interaction mechanisms – v2

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Terms and abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIC4	Artificial Intelligence Cloud Service Compliance Criteria Catalogue
AI-SEC	AI Security Evidence Collector
AMOE	Assessment and Management of Organisational Evidence
API	Application Programming Interface
AST	Abstract Syntax Tree
BSI	Bundesamt für Sicherheit in der Informationstechnik
CI/CD	Continuous Integration / Continuous Delivery
CLI	Command Line Interface
CSP	Cloud Service Provider
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
EUCS	European Cybersecurity Certification Scheme for Cloud Services
GA	Grant Agreement to the project
GASTM	Generic Abstract Syntax Tree
gRPC	Google Remote Procedure Call
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MARI	Mapping Assistant for Regulations with Intelligence
ML	Machine Learning
NLP	Natural Language Processing
OSCAL	Open Security Controls Assessment Language
PDF	Portable Document Format
PNG	Portable Network Graphics
RCM	Repository of Controls and Metrics
REST	Representational State Transfer
SARIF	Static Analysis Results Interchange Format
SVG	Scalable Vector Graphics
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TWS	Trustworthiness System
UML	Unified Modelling Language
UUID	Universally Unique Identifier
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This deliverable, the final version of the data modelling and interaction mechanisms, provides a report on the data diagrams, design and documentation of the EMERALD framework and its components. The goal of the corresponding task T1.1 in work package 1 is to coordinate the different types of data shared between the components of WP2, WP3 and WP4. The deliverable provides an overview of the data model, as well as the setup of the interactive documentation. Furthermore, the data exchange and formats are described.

D1.2 lays the foundation of the data model – the underlying work of Task 1.1. The resulting documentation serves as a common ground to develop the different components and their APIs. It should offer a high-level overview of the components – displaying the flow of the data. Technical details can be found in the overall data diagram and data format descriptions. Additionally, an overview per component is provided, so as not to be overwhelmed by details, and to be able to focus only on parts of the EMERALD framework.

The document is structured in four main parts: the data model, the component overview, the interactive documentation and finally the data exchange and format description. It starts by giving detailed insights into the data classes used in EMERALD. This is followed by an overview of each component is provided, starting with the evidence collectors (WP2) and continuing with the different components of WP3. In the interactive documentation section, the technical setup of the documentation is described. Finally, plans for the interaction mechanisms are outlined.

This is the second and final version of the previous deliverable D1.1 [1]. The contents of this deliverable have evolved depending on the different updates required by the development process of the EMERALD components and the interaction mechanisms. The updates reflect changes needed to address the requirements coming from the pilots (WP5), workflows (WP4) and the technical work packages (WP2 and WP3). As this is the final deliverable for the task T1.1, the descriptions and data models reflect the current status of the components and planned extensions. The data model and interaction mechanisms will continue to be updated; however, the expected changes are minor, and this final release can be considered stable.

1 Introduction

This section explains the goal and purpose of the deliverable, its context and its structure.

1.1 About this deliverable

This deliverable is the final release of the task T1.1 “Data modelling and information sharing mechanisms” of WP1 of the EMERALD project [2]. It shall provide an overview of the data model that is used in the EMERALD framework. Furthermore, the deliverable provides an overview of each component’s data and how it is linked to other components. The goal is to provide insights of the current state of the data used in EMERALD and how it is organized.

The data model will be used by all the components in collaboration with WP2 and WP3, as well as the **EmeraldUI** component that will be developed in WP4. The interaction mechanism between the different software components will be described and the preferred data formats to facilitate data access and sharing will be presented.

The task uses the existing data classes of the components and focuses on providing relevant information to the different partners, unfamiliar to the different components. Different abstraction layers are used to provide an overview and detailed insights. The diagrams have been adjusted over the course of the project and have been adopted to the requirements of the different components. In order not to lose track of any changes, dedicated processes (see Section 4.3) have been set up to check this.

1.2 Document structure

The document is organized into four main sections:

- Data model
- Component overview
- Interactive documentation
- Data exchange and formats

The data model overview section, **Section 2**, depicts and describes the current state of the whole data model used in EMERALD. It gives detailed insights into the inter-component relationships of the EMERALD data.

In order to have a more abstract view and not get lost in the details, an overview of the components is provided in **Section 3**. This section contains a subsection dedicated to each EMERALD component.

Section 4 describes the deployment and core implementation of the interactive documentation approach used to share the data model within the EMERALD project. There are three subsections, starting with a section describing PlantUML and how it is used to create the diagrams. This is followed by a description of the web service. Finally, the process on versioning and updating the diagrams is described.

Section 5 describes the different formats used in the project and how the components communicate. The deliverable is summarized in **Section 6**.

Finally, the current release of the interactive documentation can be found in the *APPENDIX: Release 1.4.3 of Architecture and Data Modelling* .

1.3 Updates from D1.1

This deliverable evolves from D1.1 [1], and with the ultimate goal of making the document self-contained and easier to follow, part of the content comes from D.1.1 since it has not changed. To simplify tracking progress and updates from the previous version (D1.1), Table 1 shows a summary of the changes and additions to each section of the document.

Table 1. Overview of deliverable updates with respect to D1.1

Section	Changes
1	This section is based on the previous deliverable D1.1 with the addition of this section 1.3 – Updates from D1.1.
2	The diagram of the general data model overview was updated to the current release and some more textual details regarding the arrows have been added.
3	The component data models have been updated according to the current release. Also, the text has been adapted to describe the current data classes, their properties and relations to other components.
4	The text has been extended with some details regarding the versioning of the data model.
5	The evidence examples have been updated as well as the sequence diagram section 5.2.
6	The conclusion has been updated.
7	The references have been updated.
Appendix	The appendix was updated to contain the current release at the time of writing this deliverable.

2 Data Model Overview

This section describes the final version of the EMERALD data model. The model describes the different data classes, as well as their connections within and between components. The goal is to provide insights to developers and users of the EMERALD framework. Therefore, the data diagram is presented in an interactive system¹ that is explained in more detail in Section 4. There are different abstraction layers, to allow for a “drill down” on the details.

Figure 1 shows the resulting data model for the whole EMERALD framework². It depicts each component in a separate box, whereas the background colour denotes the EMERALD work package to which it is related. Evidence collection components (WP2) are coloured in orange, and WP3 components are coloured in teal. Each component box contains the data classes that are relevant for other developers and inter-component communication. Component specific information can be found in the respective subsection of Section 3.

Please note that the Questionnaire is a subcomponent of the **RCM** and is therefore shown with a dedicated box in Figure 1. However, as the Questionnaire data model is quite large, it is not shown in Figure 1 but in the **RCM** component overview (see Figure 10).

The inter component class connections reflect the data flow if no explicit UML notation is followed. Some of the classes displayed are abstractions of the internal implementation and serve as a means to better understand and document the data structure for developers and users without the need of deep insight into the source code of the different applications. It shall help developers to track the data flow over different components alongside the API definitions that the different components offer and report in their respective documentation. As the diagram can be quite hard to track in the figure (many lines), it is recommended to use the deployed web service or release, as attached in the *APPENDIX: Release 1.4.3 of Architecture and Data Modelling*.

¹ <https://models.emerald.digital.tecnalia.dev/>

² Please note that an enlarged view of the EMERALD data model is available in *APPENDIX: Release 1.4.3 of Architecture and Data Modelling*.

3 Component Data Models

This section describes each EMERALD component from a data-oriented point of view. It covers the different evidence extraction tools, where the evidence is stored and assessed, and the tools that provide and assist with the management of the security schemes and metrics. The different views have been integrated in the interactive documentation (see *APPENDIX: Release 1.4.3 of Architecture and Data Modelling*) and can be reached via links.

Figure 2 depicts an abstracted view of the main EMERALD components and serves as a starting point for users as well as developers. The diagram shows the general data flow between all the components. The direction of the arrows indicates the direction the data flows. As also explained in the legend, a dashed line indicates that a component at the end of the arrow pulls data from the component at the other end, while a full line indicates that a component actively pushes data to another component using its API. The components are coloured according to the respective work package they are related to. The colour – work package associations can be found in the legend (see Figure 2).

Please note that the legend has been omitted in the figures of the overview of the component data models to save space, as the information is redundant.

Figure 2. Overview of the EMERALD Components

3.1 Evidence Collector Data Models

All the evidence collector components developed in WP2 collect different forms of data and extract evidence. The results are then shared in the EMERALD framework. This section describes relevant data classes used internally by them and how they relate to other components. The main connections of these components are to the **Evidence Store** and the **Repository of Controls and Metrics**.

Furthermore, the subsections below describe the main techniques for transforming raw evidence data into the EMERALD evidence class objects. Part of the data classes of the components (e.g., **Clouditor-Discovery**) are based on the CertGraphOntology model (the EMERALD Graph Ontology), which is described in D2.2 [3]. Please note that the CertGraphOntology is not a component, but a central ontology for storing evidence in a graph-based format.

3.1.1 AI-SEC

AI-SEC is an evidence collection tool that extracts various information from ML models. The data model of the tool currently consists of a single main class, *AI-SECEvidence*, which represents the extracted evidence (see Figure 3). Evidence results and closely related information are also stored in the *AI-SECEvidence* class (result). This class also contains a unique identifier (id), given resources, such as data and model (sourceFilename), and the criteria used for extracting evidence (criteriald).

AI-SEC employs various measurements to extract evidence from ML models. By providing **AI-SEC** with a set of data and a trained model, the tool can extract evidence and information about different properties of the model. The output results (evidence and information) can be a string, a vector or a matrix, depending on the measurement used.

Measurement methods are chosen based on the Criteria Catalogue for AI Cloud Services – AIC4³, such as adversarial robustness or explainability of the model. A detailed description of the annotation plan and process have been reported in D2.6 “ML model certification–v1” (M12) [4] and will receive updates in the deliverable D2.7 “ML model certification–v2” (M24).

Figure 3. Overview of the AI-SEC component data model

³ https://www.bsi.bund.de/EN/Themen/Unternehmen-und-Organisationen/Informationen-und-Empfehlungen/Kuenstliche-Intelligenz/AIC4/aic4_node.html

3.1.2 AMOE

The **AMOE – Assessment and Management of Organisational Evidence** – component extracts evidence from policy PDF documents. The component stores the uploaded files, as well as relevant metadata related to the document and metrics. There are four data classes in the data model and one enumeration relevant to external users e.g. via API (see Figure 4): *AmoePolicyFile*, *AmoeEvidence*, *AmoeComplianceResult*, *AmoeResult* and *AmoeEvidenceState*. *AmoePolicyFile* serves as an internal representation of the uploaded file, which can be linked to a Target of Evaluation via its id, while *AmoeEvidence* is the internal representation of the extracted data and is created for a set of Security Metrics during the extraction process. The *AmoeEvidence* class contains an *AmoeResult* representing the answer, score and position of the extracted result in the text. The *AmoeComplianceResult* class is used to represent the **AMOE** internal assessment result including *complianceStatus*, *complianceComment* and once it has been submitted also the *evidenceStoreId* (of the Evidence). The enumeration *AmoeEvidenceState* is the representation of possible states the *AmoeEvidence* can undergo.

The data is stored in a MongoDB⁴ and can be retrieved through the **AMOE** API endpoints. The internal data classes of **AMOE** have been adapted in the past few months, according to the requirements elicited for the **EmeraldUI** (detailed in D4.2 [5]) and further development of **AMOE**. Except for some renaming and property adjustments, the data model for **AMOE** is expected not to change throughout the future development in the **EMERALD** project.

AMOE is using an NLP (Natural Language Processing) based approach to extract evidence. It utilizes pre-trained models to select text of the policy documents that are relevant for audits. The models used at the moment of writing are specialized on different aspects, such as question answering or computing text representations (embeddings) or text classification. The extracted text passages are then stored in *AmoeEvidence* and *AmoeResult*. The relevant information stored in *AmoeEvidence* and *AmoeComplianceResult* will be transformed into an *Evidence* class object and will be forwarded to the **Evidence Store** component (see Section 3.6). Details on the approach of the **AMOE** component and its related Task 2.3 have been reported in the deliverable D2.4 “AMOE–v1” (M12) [6] and will receive an update in the deliverable D2.5 “AMOE–v2” (M24).

To ensure high quality output from **AMOE**, it is necessary to associate the text samples of the policy documents with the Security Metrics. Therefore, *AmoeEvidence* is directly related to the *SecurityMetric* class of the **Repository of Controls and Metrics** (see full data model in Figure 1, **AMOE** data model in Figure 4, and **RCM** data model in Figure 10). The plans on annotation and the detailed description of the process will be conducted in the Task 2.3 and reported in the previously stated deliverable (D2.5).

Furthermore, *AmoeEvidence* and *AmoeComplianceResult* are related to the **Orchestrator (Cloud Service)** and the **Evidence Store (AssessmentResult, Evidence)**, and *AmoeFile* is related to the **Orchestrator (Target of Evaluation)**.

Finally, the information from **AMOE** can be accessed via API and used via the **EmeraldUI**.

⁴ <https://www.mongodb.com/>

Figure 4. Overview of the AMOE component data model

3.1.3 Cloudfitor-Discovery

The **Cloudfitor-Discovery** component is an evidence gathering tool which extracts Cloud configurations for different Cloud resources (e.g., Virtual Machine, Object Storage, Network Interface) from several Cloud providers (e.g., Azure) via API calls.

The retrieved cloud configuration information is stored in an internal *Resource* class object that utilizes properties from the EMERALD Graph Ontology. While the Graph Ontology is described in D2.1 [7], the properties can be found within the ontology. An example of a Resource object of a Virtual Machine can be found in Listing 1.

Besides the *Resource* class object, the **Cloudfitor-Discovery** stores the gathered information in the *CloudfitorDiscoveryEvidence* class object (see Figure 5), which is the same class object as the *Evidence* provided by the **Evidence Store** component. Evidence objects are stored in the **Evidence Store** component, a description of the *Evidence* can be found in Section 3.6.

The link from the **Orchestrator** to the *targetOfEvaluationId* property in the *CloudfitorDiscoveryEvidence* class refers to the *Target of Evaluation* defined in the **Orchestrator** component (see Section 3.5).

Details on the approach of the **Cloudfitor-Discovery** component and its related Task 2.5 have been reported in deliverable D2.8 “Runtime evidence extractor–v1” (M12) [8] and will be updated in Deliverable D2.9 “Runtime evidence extractor–v2” (M24).

Figure 5. Overview of the Cloudfitor-Discovery component data model

```
message VirtualMachine {
  option (resource_type_names) = "VirtualMachine";
  option (resource_type_names) = "Compute";
  option (resource_type_names) = "CloudResource";
  option (resource_type_names) = "Resource";

  google.protobuf.Timestamp creation_time = 2132;
  string id = 15888 [(buf.validate.field).required = true];
  bool internet_accessible_endpoint = 11229;
  map<string, string> labels = 12634;
  string name = 5434 [(buf.validate.field).required = true];
  // The raw field contains the raw information that is used to
  // fill in the fields of the ontology.
  string raw = 17236;
  ActivityLogging activity_logging = 17610;
  AutomaticUpdates automatic_updates = 7698;
  repeated string block_storage_ids = 14852;
  BootLogging boot_logging = 4303;
  EncryptionInUse encryption_in_use = 5839;
  GeoLocation geo_location = 17337;
  MalwareProtection malware_protection = 5352;
  repeated string network_interface_ids = 150;
  OSLogging os_logging = 14872;
  repeated Redundancy redundancies = 11599;
  RemoteAttestation remote_attestation = 16051;
  optional string parent_id = 7061;
  ResourceLogging resource_logging = 17205;
  UsageStatistics usage_statistics = 4834;
}
```

Listing 1. Example of Virtual Machine properties

3.1.4 Codyze

The **Codyze** component is a static source code analysis tool which analyses source code of applications comprising Cloud services and assesses security-relevant implementation details. The analysis report presents implementation details that meet or respectively violate specified security requirements. As part of a CI/CD pipeline, **Codyze** acts as a quality and compliance gate allowing only the delivery of applications that meet security requirements and preventing it otherwise. Each update to the application's source code or new release can trigger an execution of the CI/CD pipeline and thereby **Codyze**. In addition, manual or scheduled assessments are possible.

Codyze is developed in Kotlin⁵ and uses a graph-based representation of source code utilizing the concept of a code property graph. The resulting representation is largely programming language agnostic. Thus, it facilitates the implementation of generic, reusable source code

⁵ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kotlin_\(programming_language\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kotlin_(programming_language))

analysis techniques. Currently, **Codyze** supports the programming languages C, C++, Java, Go and Python.

Within EMERALD, **Codyze** interacts with the **Orchestrator** to orchestrate its analysis, and reports its findings as evidence to the **Evidence Store** (see Figure 6). Thereby, **Codyze** generates an analysis report in SARIF⁶ (*CodyzeSarif*). This report contains raw evidence from **Codyze**'s analysis, which is persisted to the **Evidence Store** to facilitate further analysis externally to **Codyze**. Moreover, **Codyze** processes the findings in the SARIF report into evidence for the EMERALD framework. Each finding is converted into a *CodyzeEvidence* that identifies the analysed Target of Evaluation (*targetOfEvaluationId*), specifies the analysed resource (*resource*), links it to the underlying SARIF report (*sarifId*), classifies the finding according to the EMERALD ontology (*ontologyRef*) and summarizes the result (*result*).

In addition, **Codyze** will submit hashes of its evidence to the **TWS** (cf. component data model of the **TWS** in Section 3.2). The submitted hashes provide additional proof that evidence collected by **Codyze** and submitted to the **Evidence Store** are the same and have not been tampered with.

Details on the approach of the **Codyze** component and its related Task 2.2 have been reported in the deliverable D2.2 “Source Evidence Extractor–v1” (M12) [3] and will be updated in the deliverable D2.3 “Source Evidence Extractor–v2” (M24).

Figure 6. Codyze component overview

3.1.5 eknows-e3

The **eknows-e3** component – based on a platform for multi-language software analysis and documentation generation – extracts evidence from source code files. The source code files are collected from the Cloud Service environment at certain points in time. A set of predefined triggers will be available (e.g., once a week/month/etc., or upon changes) to configure the points in time according to the respective use case. **eknows-e3** analyses the collected files and extracts metadata related to the sources (e.g., from code repositories) and metrics.

eknows-e3 uses static code analysis to extract evidence. The underlying Java-based software platform provides a modular, extensible set of software components for (i) source code parsing using language-specific frontends (currently more than 16 programming languages, including

⁶ Static Analysis Results Interchange Format (SARIF), <https://docs.oasis-open.org/sarif/sarif/v2.1.0/sarif-v2.1.0.html>

Java and Python) (extraction), (ii) transformation of parsed source code into a generic abstract syntax tree (GASTM), (iii) structural and language-independent analysis of security-related information, and (iv) reporting of analysis results for security metrics. The extracted and analysed raw evidence is then forwarded to the **Evidence Store** component.

At the moment of writing, **eknows-e3** logically comprises two main data classes (see Figure 7): *EknowsAnalysisResult* and *EknowsEvidence*. Note that these internal data classes of **eknows-e3** are not 1:1 implemented as physical classes and might change in the next few months, according to the requirements defined for the **EmeraldUI** in D4.2 [5] and further needs of the pilot partners.

EknowsAnalysisResult serves as an internal representation of the result of analysing a source code file. It is based on the compilation unit, i.e. the generated abstract syntax tree (AST) model of the parsed source code retrieved by **eknows** core library. The class is identified by a unique identifier for the raw evidence (*rawId*). It contains additional (optional) attributes obtained from the compilation unit and further specialized analysis according to security metrics. These attributes denote the name of the file (*fileName*), the location (usually a source code repository) from where to collect the file (*filePath*), the date of its last modification (*modificationDate*), the line of code where the evidence was found (*lineOfCode*), the relevant part of the AST for further explanation (*relevantAST*), and the respective security metric (*metricId*).

EknowsEvidence is the internal representation of the found evidence in the source code file for a security metric during the extraction process. Based on the analysis result obtained, an evidence object is built according to the defined EMERALD evidence format, which is sent to the **Evidence Store**. It is identified by a unique identifier (*id*) and stores the analysis result as raw evidence (*rawId*). SARIF is used as format for the raw evidence, because it is a well-established format and is also used by **Codyze**. The class further contains closely related attributes, such as the time of the extraction (*timestamp*), the corresponding Target Of Evaluation (*targetOfEvaluationId*), the *toolId*, the version of the analyser for better traceability in the event of incorrect evidence (*analyzerVersion*), and the key findings of the analysis represented in ontology term (*resource*).

EknowsEvidence is related to the **Evidence Store**. Please note that an authorized connection (OAuth) is currently necessary via a **Clouditor** instance to be able to transmit evidence to the **Evidence Store**.

eknows-e3 can be configured and started via CLI (Command Line Interface) and set up via the upcoming **EmeraldUI**.

Details on the approach of the **eknows-e3** component and its related Task 2.2 have been reported in deliverable D2.2 “Source Evidence Extractor–v1” (M12) and will be updated in deliverable D2.3 “Source Evidence Extractor–v2” (M24).

Figure 7. Overview of the eknows-e3 component data model

3.2 Trustworthiness System (TWS) Data Model

The **TWS** component securely stores the information and associated metadata of evidence and assessment results on the Blockchain to be able to guarantee its integrity and transparency through the **EmeraldUI**.

Due to the use of Blockchain, sensitive information such as evidence and assessment results are not stored and just a summary of them is recorded on the Blockchain through identifiers and hashes. In fact, in the case of assessment results, two different hashes are stored: the assessment result itself and the compliance comments. The evidence and assessment result themselves are kept in a local storage - **Evidence Store** and **Assessment** components respectively.

In addition, **TWS** also records metadata information to provide some context. In the case of evidence, they are usually related to specific Target of Evaluation (`targetOfEvaluationId`) and the cloud resources to which they refer (`resourceId`). In the case of an Assessment Result, the requirement to which it refers (`requirementId`), and the associated evidence identifiers considered in the assessment (`evidenceIds`) are also stored. Finally, for both evidence and assessment results, recording information about the timestamp when they were created (`timestamp`) is also useful.

Figure 8 summarises the current data model for evidence (*TrustworthyEvidence*) and assessment results (*TrustworthyAssessmentResult*) to be recorded on the Blockchain-based **TWS**. It also shows the interactions with other components: i) with the **Assessment** component, which provides information to be recorded in the **TWS**, and from where the **TWS** retrieves the actual Evidence and Assessment Results to validate their integrity; ii) with the evidence collectors as they can optionally record evidence proofs of integrity from the source (in particular, **Codyze** will be considered as an example), and iii) with the **EmeraldUI**, which provides a graphical interface for users to automatically validate the integrity status of the Evidence and Assessment Results.

Details on the approach of the **TWS** component and its related Task 3.5 have been reported in the deliverable D3.2 “Evidence assessment and Certification–Concepts-v2” [9] (M18).

Figure 8. Overview of the Trustworthiness System component data model

3.3 Mapping Assistant for Regulations with Intelligence (MARI) Data Model

MARI – Mapping Assistant for Regulations with Intelligence - is a component that uses transformer-based tools to automatically associate:

- A security control and one, or more, security metric(s)
- Two security controls from two different certification schemes.

For the association control-metric(s), **MARI** takes as input the textual description of a security control in natural language, the textual description of a list of metrics, again in natural language, and as a result returns the list of metrics associated to that control, in descending order of relevance. To do this, the textual descriptions of the metrics and controls are transformed into feature vectors by pre-trained models.

For the association control-control, **MARI** can support a variety of certification schemes and enables the automatic associations between controls from these different schemes.

MARI interacts with **RCM**, fetching control and metric data from it, then generating both control-metric(s) and control-control associations using transformer-based models. These associations are computed based on the similarity between embeddings derived from the natural language descriptions of the controls and metrics. With the introduction of a new version of the mapping API and the addition of a similarity threshold attribute, only associations with high similarity scores are returned to **RCM**.

Figure 9 shows the second version of the **MARI** data model, based on the **RCM** data model. The **RCM** data classes *SecurityMetric* and *SecurityControl* are taken as input to produce two new data classes (*Control2ControlAssociation* and *Metrics2ControlAssociation*). These represent the associations generated by **MARI**'s processing. Details on the approach of **MARI** component and its related Task 3.3 have been reported in D3.2 [9].

Figure 9. Overview of the MARI component data model

3.4 Repository of Controls and Metrics (RCM) Data Model

The **Repository of Controls and Metrics (RCM)** provides a central point in EMERALD framework where the certification schemes are stored and managed. The repository can contain different schemes and includes a complete information of each scheme, with the corresponding categorization.

The data model of the RCM has been adapted from the first version, that was EUCS-centered [10]. In this second version, the BSI C5⁷ and AIC4⁸ schemes have also been incorporated to the **RCM**. Each schema has its own structure, but all share a common ground: they consist in a catalogue of controls (also called criteria), grouped into several areas or objectives. Main changes are related to the *SecurityControl* class, that is now the basic of the *SecurityControlFramework*. The *SecurityRequirement*, a particular class to map the EUCS structure, remains only internal to the **RCM** component and is mainly used in the EUCS Questionnaire.

⁷https://www.bsi.bund.de/SharedDocs/Downloads/EN/BSI/CloudComputing/ComplianceControlsCatalogue/2020/C5_2020.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=3

⁸https://www.bsi.bund.de/SharedDocs/Downloads/EN/BSI/CloudComputing/AIC4/AI-Cloud-Service-Compliance-Criteria-Catalogue_AIC4.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=4

Figure 10 shows the resulting data model. The principal data classes implemented in the **RCM** are *SecurityControlFramework*, *SecurityCategory* and *SecurityControl* that reflect the organization of a general framework. Along with these, some other auxiliary entities are implemented, such as *SimilarControls* and *ControlMetricMap*, that support the mapping among controls of different schemes and the mapping of metrics to controls, and *ImplementationGuidelines*, that helps the user with the implementation of controls. **RCM** also incorporates the definition of the *SecurityMetric* class used in EMERALD to define what to measure to assess the collected evidence.

The **RCM** classes have interactions with other EMERALD components as follows:

- *SecurityControlFramework*, *SecurityControl* and *SecurityMetric* are related with the **Orchestrator**, which internally manages the schemes.
- *SecurityMetric* is also related with the **AMOE** and the **Assessment** components.
- *SecurityMetric* and *SecurityControl* are also shared with the **MARI** component.

RCM calls the **MARI** component to generate control-metric(s) and control-control mappings. The result is stored in the **RCM**, where it is accessible to the rest of components. The last version of the mapping API includes a similarity “threshold” attribute, so that only associations with higher similarity scores are returned to **RCM**. This avoids the return of a list with all the possible similar items, which is the standard operating mode of the tool. The “statusMari” and “statusUser” attributes have been introduced in each mapped item to differentiate and maintain controlled the original mapping returned by **MARI** and the changes done by the user to it, respectively.

Another functionality offered by the **RCM** is a Questionnaire to provide users the possibility to perform a self-assessment to check compliance with the EUCS scheme. The Questionnaire-related data classes have been slightly modified since the previous version by removing some redundant links and changing some names to better reflect the underlying data which are enclosed in a box in the diagram (see Figure 10). These data classes are as follows: *UserAnswer*, *QuestionnaireAssuranceLevel*, *Question*, *QuestionAnswer*, *UserAnswerNonConformities*, and *jhiUser*. All these entities are devoted to (i) Implement several questions per requirement, (ii) manage the responses given; (iii) calculate the results for this specific user, and (iv) offer the degree of compliance with the EUCS scheme regarding the selected assurance level.

Finally, the **EmeraldUI** component is also related with the data entities used in the **RCM** to provide the final user with a graphical view of the schemes and all the associated information.

Details on the approach of the **RCM** component and its related Task 3.2 have been reported in D3.2 [9].

Figure 10. Overview of the RCM component data model

3.5 Orchestrator Data Model

The **Orchestrator** is the central management and orchestration component in EMERALD. Its main purpose is to hold all dynamic information about the current audit process, such as the Target of Evaluation, Assessment Results, and the final Certificate state (see Figure 11). Furthermore, it fetches static data from the **RCM**, such as the available schemes and its associated metrics. For performance reasons this data (*SecurityControlFramework*, *SecurityControlCategory*, *SecurityControl* and *SecurityMetric*) is cached in the **Orchestrator**. The most important dynamic data classes are:

- *Target of Evaluation*, which holds the logical representation of a single service, which aims to be certified.
- *Audit Scope*, which takes an existing *targetOfEvaluationId* and combines it with one dedicated security catalogue to produce a Certificate.
- *Certificate*, which is the data class representing different states and is related to the *EvaluationResults*.
- *Control*, which is the neutral representation of either a control, requirement or objective (this definition of Control is similar to the term defined in OSCAL⁹). Since every *SecurityControlFramework*/security scheme uses different names, the **Orchestrator** normalizes them in the *Control* data class. In addition, each *Control* can have sub-controls, which allows to include different *SecurityControlFrameworks* in EMERALD.

Details on the approach of the **Orchestrator** component and its related Task 3.1 have been reported in D3.2 “Evidence assessment and Certification – Concepts – v2” [9].

⁹ <https://pages.nist.gov/OSCAL/learn/concepts/terminology/#control>

Figure 11. Overview of the Orchestrator component data model

3.6 Evidence Store Data Model

The **Evidence Store** is the central component to store evidence from the evidence collector components, which send the generated evidence directly to the **Evidence Store**. The main data class is *Evidence*, which holds the necessary information regarding the collected evidence (see Figure 12) and whose important fields are the following:

- A unique identifier (id) for each evidence. It needs to be a UUID
- timestamp describing when the evidence was created
- targetOfEvaluationId of the Target of Evaluation the evidence belongs to
- toolId is the ID of the evidence collector tool that created the evidence (such as **Codyze**, **eknows-e3**, **Clouditor-Discovery**, ...)
- resource contains the resource properties of the discovered resource. It is described according to the terms of the EMERALD Graph Ontology in D2.10 [11].

The evidence is sent to the **Assessment** component and can be retrieved via the **Orchestrator** API.

Details on the approach of the **Evidence Store** component and its related Task 3.1 is reported in D3.2 “Evidence assessment and Certification–Concepts-v2” [9].

Figure 12. Overview of the Evidence Store component data model

3.7 Assessment Data Model

The **Assessment** component assesses the evidence stored in the **Evidence Store** by using the metric definitions from the **RCM**. The needed metrics are retrieved from the **Orchestrator** and the evidence are sent directly from the **Evidence Store** to the **Assessment**. The important data classes are the following:

- *Metric* contains the metadata and a link to the corresponding *MetricImplementation*
- *MetricImplementation* contains the implementation used by the assessment with the specific code and the code language
- *MetricConfiguration* contains the target value, and the operator used in the assessment and can be specified separately for each Target of Evaluation

- *AssessmentResult* contains the result of the assessment, including the used *evidenceId*, *metricId* and *metricConfiguration*.

The *AssessmentResults* are sent to the **Trustworthiness System** and can be retrieved via the API endpoints of the **Orchestrator**. Figure 13 depicts the diagram for the **Assessment** data model.

Details on the approach of the **Assessment** component and its related Task 3.4 is reported in D3.2 “Evidence assessment and Certification–Concepts-v2” [9].

Figure 13. Overview of the Assessment component data model

3.8 Evaluation Data Model

The main purpose of the **Evaluation** component is to map the measurements of individual metrics (i.e., assessment results) and combine them according to the mapping of a metric to a Control. This is defined as an *EvaluationResult* (see Figure 14), the most important fields of which are:

- Its id, which is a UUID to make it unique
- The combination of the Target of Evaluation (through its *targetOfEvaluationId*) and a control (through its *controlled* and *associated catalogId* identifiers)
- A timestamp
- A status, which can either be *compliant*, *not compliant* or *waiting for more data*
- Optionally, a second *validUntil* field, which describes the validity of this result. This is mainly used for evaluation results that are created manually (e.g., for controls which cannot be automatically measured).

Usually, one or more metrics define the compliance state of a control. Currently, all the assessment results need to be compliant for the evaluation result to be compliant. This might change in the future if more sophisticated logical operations are needed. For example, it could be possible that either one or another metric is sufficient to demonstrate compliance to the control.

Details on the approach of the **Evaluation** component and its related Task 3.4 is reported in D3.2 “Evidence assessment and Certification–Concepts-v2” [9].

Figure 14. Overview of the Evaluation component data model

4 Interactive Documentation

This section describes the web-based documentation approach used to share the data model within the EMERALD project. The main technologies used are PlantUML¹⁰, Nginx¹¹ web service and Gitlab¹². The main objective is to have a centralized documentation that can be viewed from any device, without the need to install any tools.

4.1 PlantUML

To allow for easy text-based creation of the data model, the PlantUML tool was chosen. This tool supports a wide range of diagrams – some of which have included in our documentation e.g., class diagrams, sequence diagrams, component diagrams. As the diagrams are based on structured text, very similar to common programming languages, the implementation is straight forward and can therefore be easily adapted into code or vice versa.

PlantUML allows to render the diagrams in different output formats. The most commonly used in the project are PNG and SVG. The latter is important for the web-service – the option ‘!pragma svginteractive true’ switches the diagrams from static boxes to dynamically highlighted on hover or click. As it might be hard to track connected classes in a huge class diagram, a class can be clicked or hovered and all related classes are highlighted as well.

Figure 15 depicts an example: the **Evaluation** component was clicked, and the direct neighbour **Orchestrator** is highlighted, whereas the other links and components are faded.

Figure 15. Interactive SVG - highlight neighbours on click

Furthermore, PlantUML allows to set variables and themes to use the EMERALD colour scheme on all diagrams. This is convenient as the colour scheme can be imported for each diagram and does not need to be set manually for each element. The different diagram files can be included in other files, which reduces redundant information, and the main classes of each subcomponent need to be defined in a single file. The names of the components are set as variables including links to the overview diagrams – so no manual linking is required.

4.2 Web Service

To make the diagrams more accessible, a simple html page was created that includes some basic JavaScript functionalities to switch the diagrams displayed. The landing page (<https://models.emerald.digital.tecnalia.dev/>) shows an overview of the components (see Figure 16). Users can click component titles to switch to the respective overview diagram.

¹⁰ <https://plantuml.com/>

¹¹ <https://nginx.org/en/>

¹² <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/GitLab>

Furthermore, a navigation bar at the top of the page allows quick access to the component overview (“Components” menu option) or the data diagram page (“Data diagram” menu option). The idea is to start with a generic overview and then drill down to see the details of a component. Although the data diagram is quite large, you can focus on a single component by clicking on it.

Figure 16. Landing page of the interactive documentation

4.2.1 Implementation details

Once the diagrams are rendered, the interactive documentation can be deployed locally without any need of a web service by simply opening the index.html file. However, for ease of access - and to always have access to the newest release - we are using Dockerfiles¹³ to generate a nginx based image that can be deployed on the EMERALD Kubernetes cluster.

The structure of the web service is as follows:

```
./index.html
./imgs/logo.svg
./out/*_data.svg
./out/*_component.svg
./out/*_Sequence_Diagram.svg
```

The index.html file contains the basic structure and scripts to load the diagrams. The EMERALD logo is stored in /imgs. The rendered diagrams are stored in /out and are loaded on demand. This implementation is portable to any device that supports a modern web browser by simply copying the files. In the Nginx web service, the files are located in /usr/share/nginx/html.

¹³ <https://docs.docker.com/reference/dockerfile/>

4.3 Data model versioning

As the PlantUML based diagrams contain text/code, the files can be used in versioning systems such as git¹⁴. This allows for different organisational processes, which are not possible in common online tools with graphical support (e.g., draw.io¹⁵ – although it allows versioning, there are no processes to keep different versions of the diagrams and proposed changes, as it is possible using text-based diagrams and git + GitLab¹⁶). Different versions of the diagrams can be stored in commits, and merge requests can be created to deal with changes to the diagrams.

The process to add changes to the data model has been defined as follows: major changes are completed in a separate branch – when finished, a merge request should be created in the EMERALD GitLab and the changes will be reviewed to check for inconsistencies and breaks to the interactive, web-service-based deployment. After the review, the new version will be merged, which triggers the build pipeline, and a new release will be deployed to the EMERALD Kubernetes cluster. New release numbering is automated using the CI/CD strategy from EMERALD as reported in other WP1 deliverables such as D1.7 [12]. The changelog and updated release (if done automatically) is based on the commit messages. The current release numbering has been included in the web page and can be viewed in the top right corner. Once merged, the latest release version of the diagrams will be available to all developers and can be retrieved at <https://models.emerald.digital.tecnalia.dev/>. If there are any problems, or additional diagrams are needed, Gitlab's issue functionality can be used to document, communicate and coordinate the required changes.

¹⁴ <https://git-scm.com/>

¹⁵ <https://www.draw.io>

¹⁶ <https://gitlab.com/>

5 Data Exchange and Formats

This section provides a short overview of the planned data exchange approach, as well as the formats used. Although all EMERALD components use different data types, they all communicate in a standardized way and format, which speeds up development as components do not need to build special data connectors for the different tools.

5.1 Interaction mechanisms between components

The interaction between the components will be implemented using REST¹⁷ – representational state transfer. Each component is using and/or serving REST-APIs that are documented in the OpenAPI¹⁸ specification files. This helps developers to share the different endpoints and allows to generate code for client interfaces. Some components may also offer gRPC connections (Remote Procedure Call framework by Google) to share data between closely related components such as **Evidence Store** and **Assessment**. The most common format for REST-API will be JSON¹⁹, as it allows for easy access of attribute-value pairs and arrays.

Listing 2 shows the JSON example for a piece of evidence that is sent from **AMOE** to the **Evidence Store**. Similarly, Listing 3 shows a more extensive example for data represented in JSON and how it is used by some EMERALD components, such as **Clouditor-Discovery**.

```
{
  "id": "b11a1b4b-4cff-4135-afbb-f6e30364d881",
  "timestamp": "2024-06-26T18:23:45.123456",
  "target_of_evaluation_id": "3f1c2e4c-8bd5-45d1-a6a3-0f9a9a8e4d35",
  "tool_id": "amoe",
  "resource": {
    "policyDocument": {
      "id": "165483",
      "name": "165483",
      "raw": "password must contain more than 15 characters",
      "amoe_result": true
    }
  }
}
```

Listing 2. AMOE example evidence in JSON

¹⁷ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/REST>

¹⁸ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/OpenAPI_Specification

¹⁹ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/JSON>

```

{
  "id": "11100000-1000-0001-0000-000000011111",
  "timestamp": "2020-05-22T20:32:05Z",
  "targetOfEvaluationId": "00000000-0000-0000-0000-000000000000",
  "toolId": "Clouditor Evidence Collection",
  "resource": {
    "objectStorageService": {
      "creationTime": "2023-07-09T10:35:18.246911100Z",
      "id":
"/subscriptions/XXXXX/resourcegroups/democlouditorhappy/providers/micro
soft.storage/storageaccounts/democlouditordiagnositics",
      "labels": {
        "owner": "clouditor"
      },
      "name": "democlouditordiagnositics",
      "geoLocation": {
        "region": "westeurope"
      },
      "httpEndpoint": {
        "url":
"https://democlouditordiagnositics.[file,blob].core.windows.net/",
        "transportEncryption": {
          "enabled": true,
          "enforced": true,
          "protocol": "TLS",
          "protocolVersion": 1.2,
          "cipherSuites": []
        }
      },
      "parentId":
"/subscriptions/XXXXX/resourcegroups/democlouditorhappy"
    }
  }
}

```

Listing 3. Clouditor example evidence in JSON

Some components will offer data import / export functionality, in particular the **Repository of Controls and Metrics** will allow import of security schemes using the OSCAL²⁰ format. The API description and more details on the format will be described in the future deliverable D3.4 “Evidence assessment and Certification–Implementation-v2” (M24). The OSCAL format allows different file types and data formats such as YAML²¹ and JSON. Listing 4 shows a tentative example of the mapping of an EUCS Requirement in OSCAL. It can be seen how the parts of the Control (*ops-02*) are specified using the OSCAL elements “id”, “title”, “properties”, and with “parts” and “prose”; the Requirements are implemented with “parts” within the upper “parts”

²⁰ <https://pages.nist.gov/OSCAL/>

²¹ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/YAML>

of Control. The Requirement ID (OPS-02.3) is specified with “properties”, and the requirement itself with “prose”.

```

"controls": [
  {
    "id": "ops-02",
    "title": "CAPACITY MANAGEMENT - MONITORING",
    "properties": [
      {
        "name": "label",
        "value": "OPS-02"
      }
    ],
    "parts": [
      {
        "id": "ops_02_obj",
        "name": "control-objective",
        "prose": "The capacities of critical resources such as
personnel and IT resources are monitored."
      },
      {
        "id": "ops-02_smt",
        "name": "statement",
        "parts": [
          {
            "id": "ops-02_smt.3",
            "name": "item",
            "properties": [
              {
                "name": "label",
                "value": "OPS-02.3"
              }
            ],
            "prose": "The provisioning and de-provisioning of
cloud services shall be automatically monitored to guarantee fulfilment of
OPS-02.1"
          }
        ]
      }
    ]
  }
]

```

Listing 4. An EUCS Requirement mapping in OSCAL

5.2 Sequence diagrams

To illustrate the interactions between the components, sequence diagrams have been created and extended as part of the work of Task 1.1. Additional documentation will be provided which can be included in the interactive PlantUML diagrams. The sequence diagrams for the rest of the components have been added to the interactive documentation and have been reported in the

deliverable D1.3 “EMERALD solution architecture-v1” (M12) [13] and will receive updates in the deliverable D1.4 “EMERALD solution architecture-v2” (M24).

6 Conclusions

This document provides an overview of the overall EMERALD data model, as well as a more detailed view of the component data models. The data model overview depicts all the classes of the different EMERALD components. Furthermore, it shows, how the classes are linked together and the direction of the inter component data exchange is reflected.

The data model is presented in a web service, to allow interactive investigation of the different diagrams. The diagrams are based on text instructions using PlantUML and then rendered in SVG files. This allows the diagrams to be versioned and the various functionalities of the EMERALD GitLab repository can be used to manage and coordinate the updates. The basic idea of this interactive documentation is to start with an abstract overview (landing page) and then drill down to the different components of interest. The different classes and components of the diagrams can be clicked/hovered to navigate and highlight direct connections.

Finally, this deliverable describes the main data format that will be used for data exchange between EMERALD components and external sources – JSON. To provide more insight, an example for **AMOE** evidence and another for **Clouditor-Discovery** evidence have been provided. The **Repository of Controls and Metrics (RCM)** will provide import/export functionality of security schemes in OSCAL format – for which a JSON example was also provided.

The data diagrams will be updated according to the needs and changes of the different components. These changes will be subject to the described processes in this deliverable, shared with the consortium in different version releases, and deployed in the EMERALD Kubernetes infrastructure. Although, this is the last deliverable for this task in EMERALD, future updates to the data model (e.g. error corrections) will be collected and described in the EMERALD development git environment and the new releases of the interactive web service will continue to be deployed alongside the EMERALD components.

7 References

- [1] EMERALD Consortium, “D1.1 Data modelling and interaction mechanisms - v1,” 2024.
- [2] EMERALD Consortium, “EMERALD - Annex 1 - Description of Action - GA 101120688,” 2022.
- [3] EMERALD Consortium, “D2.2 Source Evidence Extractor – v1: Evidence extraction from source code that can be integrated with the certification graph,” 2024.
- [4] EMERALD Consortium, “D2.6 ML model certification – v1: Security and privacy preserving evidence that can be integrated with the certification graph,” 2024.
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- [6] EMERALD Consortium, “D2.4 AMOE – v1: Evidence extraction from policy documents that can be integrated with the certification graph,” 2024.
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- [10] ENISA, “EUCS - Cloud Services Scheme,” [Online]. Available: <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/eucs-cloud-service-scheme>. [Accessed July 2024].
- [11] EMERALD Consortium, “D2.10 Certification Graph -v1,” 2025.
- [12] EMERALD Consortium, “D1.7 EMERALD integrated solution - v1,” 2025.
- [13] EMERALD Consortium, “D1.3 EMERALD solution architecture - v1,” 2024.

APPENDIX: Release 1.4.3 of Architecture and Data Modelling

In order to allow the readers of this document to consult the documentation and data model themselves, the current version of the files have been archived in a zip file. The contents are images of the different data models, as well as a webpage to aid in navigation. The 1.4.3 release version of the interactive documentation is available here: [D1.2 Appendix Release 1-4-3 of Architecture and Data Modelling](#)

To open the interactive documentation locally, you need to extract the zip file. Then navigate to the “architecture_and_data_model” folder and open the index.html file in a common web browser.